

Popliteal Artery Entrapment Syndrome. Case Report in an Elderly Patient

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ABSTRACT

Popliteal entrapment syndrome is a condition caused by vascular and musculotendinous abnormalities in the embryological development of the popliteal fossa. This condition can lead to thrombosis, stenosis, or aneurysms of the popliteal artery or vein, causing symptoms such as claudication, chronic pain, or acute ischemia. We present the diagnostic and surgical approach of a 73-year-old male patient with type 1 popliteal artery entrapment syndrome and arterial thrombosis. A tenomyotomy of the medial gastrocnemius muscle and popliteal thrombectomy were performed with intraoperative arteriography, which resulted in the recovery of distal pulses. Because this is an underdiagnosed condition that can be asymptomatic, it should be recognized and considered even in older adults with unexplained acute ischemia. Magnetic resonance angiography is essential for diagnosis, and open surgery remains the treatment of choice.

KEYWORDS: Popliteal artery entrapment syndrome, acute ischemia, elderly, vascular surgery.

ABBREVIATIONS: magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), magnetic resonance angiography (MRA), maximum intensity projection (MIP).

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INTRODUCTION

Popliteal entrapment syndrome is an anatomical abnormality (vascular or musculotendinous) of embryological origin in the development of the popliteal fossa, which can lead to stenosis, thrombosis, or aneurysms (1, 2).

The anatomical basis of popliteal entrapment was first described by Anderson Stuart, a medical student in Edinburgh, in 1879. In 1965, the term was coined by Love and Whelan, meaning compression of the popliteal artery caused by an abnormal anatomical relationship between the vessel and adjacent musculotendinous structures. This can cause functional impairment, vascular microtrauma, hematomas, thrombosis, embolizations, aneurysms, or dissection of the popliteal artery, leading to acute ischemia with or without distal embolization (3, 4).

This is believed to be caused by abnormal embryological development, in which there is a struggle for space in the

popliteal fossa between the vascular bundle and the muscle groups. The most common abnormalities include delayed migration of the medial branch of the gastrocnemius muscle, leading to medial displacement of the popliteal artery (6, 7, 8).

Another pathophysiological mechanism in athletes is muscle hypertrophy, which causes forced compression of the neurovascular bundle (9).

It is a condition characterized by an insidious and progressive course of pain in the affected lower limb, accompanied by claudication, exercise intolerance, and calf pain with exertion relieved by rest. It should be suspected in patients under 50 years of age with this type of symptoms (10, 11).

The differential diagnosis for patients with exercise-induced chronic leg pain includes chronic compartment syndrome, unresolved muscle strain, medial tibial stress syndrome,

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fibular and tibial stress syndrome, fractures, fascial defects, nerve entrapment syndrome, atherosclerotic vascular claudication, and herniated disk. Due to the variability of differential diagnoses, this condition is often underdiagnosed (12, 13).

The objective of this report is to describe a case with an atypical presentation of popliteal entrapment in an elderly man with acute arterial insufficiency and no previous symptoms (14, 15).

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 73-year-old male patient had smoked one pack a day for 28 years, having quit smoking 20 years prior to admission. He had no history of chronic degenerative disease. His condition began 8 days prior to admission, with pain in the popliteal region and calf of his right lower limb, which worsened with walking. One day prior to admission, he presented with pallor and hypothermia below the knee in his right lower limb, with no history of trauma or strenuous exercise.

Physical examination revealed pallor and hypothermia in the right lower limb, a palpable femoral pulse of adequate intensity, and absent popliteal, dorsalis pedis, and posterior tibial pulses, the latter two with monophasic flow present on linear Doppler examination.

The diagnostic impression was acute popliteal artery occlusion, and an approach was initiated to rule out embolism or thrombosis. The imaging studies showed an echocardiogram with no evidence of intracavitary thrombi, angiotomography and arterial Doppler ultrasound with evidence of popliteal artery occlusion, compatible with thrombosis, no plaques, ulcers, proximal aorto-iliac aneurysms, potential sites of atherothromboembolization, or ipsilateral popliteal aneurysm were observed (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. Multiplanar reconstruction in a coronal oblique plane at the level of the right popliteal fossa showing the medialized popliteal artery, with the presence of a hypodense intraluminal thrombus that expands the arterial diameter.

Based on the findings, surgical treatment was decided upon. Arterial exploration, thrombectomy, and intraoperative arteriography were performed, revealing segmental stenosis

and medialization of the popliteal artery. Medicated balloon angioplasty was performed, restoring distal circulation (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2. Arteriography. Upper left: Filling defect in the right popliteal artery and presence of collateral circulation. Upper right: Balloon angioplasty. Lower left: Blood flow is restored after balloon angioplasty. Lower right: Shows partial improvement in distal blood flow after angioplasty.

Due to both the segmental stenosis and medialization of the popliteal artery, and the absence of a proximal thromboembolic focus, the etiology was suspected to be entrapment or cystic degeneration of the popliteal artery. Therefore, an MRA of the lower limbs was ordered the following day, documenting an anomalous proximal insertion of the medial gastrocnemius muscle, leading to entrapment and thrombosis of the popliteal artery (Figure 3 and 4).

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FIGURE 3. MRI of the right pelvic limb, which identifies an anomalous insertion of the medial gastrocnemius muscle, which is inserted into the most lateral aspect of the medial femoral condyle, causing medialization of the popliteal artery and luminal stenosis.

FIGURE 4. Contrast-enhanced MRA with MIP reconstruction in the coronal plane again makes evident the filling defect of the popliteal artery with recanalization of distal flow by collateral vessels.

It was decided to explore the popliteal fossa with a medial approach, identifying extrinsic compression of the popliteal artery by the medial gastrocnemius muscle. A tenomyotomy was performed, as well as exploration of the popliteal artery with thrombectomy and primary closure, restoring vessel patency and distal circulation (Figure 5).

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FIGURE 5. Popliteal fossa with medial approach, identifying extrinsic compression of the popliteal artery by the medial head of the medial gastrocnemius muscle (A). Vascular dissection of the pulseless artery and muscle is initiated (B). Separation of the popliteal artery (Red arrow) and tenotomy of the medial head of the gastrocnemius (Yellow arrow) is performed (C). Vascular control of the popliteal artery even without a pulse (D). Longitudinal arteriotomy and thrombectomy are performed, identifying partial thrombosis of the popliteal artery, immediately presenting adequate retrograde and antegrade flow, subsequent primary closure of the arteriotomy with non-absorbable 6-0 vascular suture (E).

The patient made satisfactory progress in the immediate and immediate postoperative period, with no complications associated with the surgical procedure. Currently, dorsalis pedis and posterior tibial pulses are present and of adequate amplitude.

DISCUSSION

Anatomical variability is related to the embryonic development of the structures that make up the popliteal fossa. The popliteal artery and the medial head of the gastrocnemius muscle develop at approximately the same time. The popliteal artery originates from the extension of the femoral artery proximally and the sciatic artery distally. Eventually, the femoral artery dominates, and the sciatic artery involutes (1-4).

Anomalies related to the position of the popliteal artery, the medial head of the gastrocnemius, and the popliteal muscles constitute the different types of popliteal artery entrapment syndrome. Aberrant migration of the medial head during embryonic development can lead to malpositioning of the muscle in relation to the popliteal vessels. Although this pathology is present from birth, it manifests later, probably due to changes related to hypertrophy and use of the gastrocnemius muscle (5, 7).

The incidence of this syndrome in the general population ranges from 0.17% to 3.5%. Eighty-five percent of diagnosed patients are men, and 60% of cases occur in male athletes under 30 years of age. Up to 30% of these cases may be bilaterally symptomatic. In our clinical case, the patient was

a man with unilateral symptoms, but the age range was higher than that reported in the literature, with very rare case reports in people over 60 years of age, with an incidence of less than 0.01%, and may be underdiagnosed (1, 2, 3).

The incidence of the disease has increased in recent years. Classically, patients, primarily athletes, without cardiovascular risk factors who present with intermittent, progressive claudication, paresthesia, pallor, and hypothermia, may present with gastrocnemius muscle hypertrophy. Physical examination should include a comparative study of distal pulses with plantar dorsiflexion, which may produce decreased, uneven, or even absent pulses. The sudden onset of more intense pain in a young adult after an episode of intense exercise should raise suspicion of this process (8, 9, 10).

However, in this age group, the condition could be due to risk factors related to age-related musculoskeletal changes or normal biomechanics of the affected limb, unusual physical activity, trauma, fractures, among others (12, 13).

Anatomical popliteal artery entrapment syndrome is classified into five types, according to the anatomical abnormalities described by Bettiga et al. (10), although a modified classification occasionally exists that includes type VI, Functional Popliteal Artery Entrapment Syndrome. This syndrome does not include inherited anatomical abnormalities and is due to repeated microtraumas that cause connective tissue growth, destruction of the internal elastic lamina, and damage to smooth muscles, resulting in fibrosis and scarring that can lead to thrombosis, embolization, or aneurysmal degeneration. It should also be considered that tibial nerve involvement can occur with all five anatomical subtypes of popliteal artery entrapment syndrome, causing neuropathic pain (1, 4, 5, 9).

Although type 2 is the most common type, our clinical case shows type 1 disease, which is due to an aberrant medial course of the artery around a normally inserted gastrocnemius muscle, reported in 15 to 25% (6, 7, 9) (Figure 6).

FIGURE 6. Types of popliteal artery entrapment syndrome. Popliteal fossa área. By Encinas-García Jorge A.

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For the diagnostic approach, arterial Doppler ultrasound is used to evidence thrombosis and if it does not exist, dynamic ultrasound is performed with standing maneuvers, in neutral position and dorsiflexion, being a quick, economical and noninvasive initial detection test. Findings of arterial compromise or prominent collaterals in the popliteal fossa suggest the diagnosis. Angiotomography and magnetic resonance allow us to confirm the diagnosis when there is occlusion of the popliteal artery; however, they do not allow dynamic maneuvers. MRI is the gold standard to define the anatomy of the popliteal fossa since it can locate abnormal muscle positioning. Angiography can be performed, which despite being an invasive method allows maneuvers; however, it does not obtain the anatomical information provided by magnetic resonance. All complementary studies were used for the diagnostic approach of the case, allowing better programming of the treatment to be carried out (8, 10). Treatment will depend on the symptoms and progression of the disease. For symptomatic patients, surgery with popliteal artery release allows for the definitive restoration of normal anatomy, preventing future thrombosis, as happened in this patient (5, 11, 12).

It is performed via a posterior or medial approach, dividing the muscle or musculotendinous band. The artery can then be palpated to determine its patency and determine whether embolectomy or a bypass is required. It is important to note that muscle reconstruction is not required, as its division does not result in functional limitations. The medial approach may be preferable for types I and II, while the posterior approach is preferable for types III and IV. The management of functional popliteal artery entrapment syndrome is controversial; endovascular treatment is not recommended, as it does not release the underlying structure, and its long-term efficacy is unclear. The open approach has a success rate of almost 100%, which is why it is the recommended treatment for these cases (13, 14, 15).

In follow-up, postoperative surveillance with arterial Doppler ultrasound is recommended at 1, 3, 6 and 12 months and annually thereafter (15).

CONCLUSION

Popliteal artery entrapment syndrome is an underdiagnosed condition. It should be suspected in young patients with claudication or symptoms of early ischemia. We must take into account that a significant percentage of the population with this syndrome is asymptomatic, which is why a later onset of the condition should not be ruled out, as in this case. Magnetic resonance imaging will be the gold standard for establishing the diagnosis. An open approach, as in the patient presented previously, will be the treatment of choice.

REFERENCES

- I. Hameed M, Coupland A, Davies AH. Popliteal artery entrapment syndrome: an approach to diagnosis and management. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*; 2018,0(0):2017-098704. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2017-098704>
- II. Wady H, Badar Z, Farooq Z, Shaw P, Kobayashi K. Avoiding the Trap of Misdiagnosis: Valuable Teaching Points Derived from a Case of Longstanding Popliteal Artery Entrapment Syndrome. *Case Rep Med*. 2018;2018:3214561. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/3214561>
- III. Barabas AP, Macfarlane R. Popliteal artery entrapment syndrome. *British Journal of Hospital Medicine*.1985; 34(5):304–306. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/3915437>
- IV. Kwon YJ, Kwon TW, Gwon JG, Cho YP, Hwang SJ, Go KY. Anatomical popliteal artery entrapment syndrome. *Annals of Surgical Treatment and Research*;2018,94(5): 262. <https://doi.org/10.4174/ast.2018.94.5.262>
- V. Altinsoy HB, Alatas O, Khalil E, Kara KA, Okten CC, Dogan OF. A Very Rare Cause of Lower Limb Ischemia in Young People: Popliteal Artery Entrapment. *Open Cardiovasc Med J*. 2018;12:18-28. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1874192401812010018>
- VI. Leong YXC, See PLP. Clinics in diagnostic imaging (185). *Singapore Med J*. 2018;59(4):177-182. <https://doi.org/10.11622/smedj.2018045>
- VII. Shortell C, et al. Popliteal Artery Occlusive Disease. *Medscape*;2018,1(1):12–14. <https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/461910-overview>
- VIII. Hislop M, Brideaux A, Dhupelia S. Functional popliteal artery entrapment syndrome: use of ultrasound guided Botox injection as a non-surgical treatment option. *Skeletal Radiol*. 2017;46(9):1241-1248. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00256-017-2686-6>
- IX. Wang X, Zhang H, Yan J, Lu Z. Successful endovascular treatment of popliteal artery entrapment syndrome: a case report with 3-years follow-up. *J Thromb Thrombolysis*. 2017;44(1):112-117. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11239-017-1505-1>
- X. Georgiotis S, Aggelakas J, Salemis N, Elias C, Georgiou C. Diagnosis and surgical approach of popliteal artery entrapment syndrome: a retrospective study. *Vasc Health Risk Manag*. 2008;4(1):83-8. <https://doi.org/10.2147/vhrm.2008.04.01.83>
- XI. Soobrah R, Nawaz A, Hussain T. Popliteal artery entrapment syndrome presenting with acute limb ischaemia: A case report. *Case Reports in Medicine*; 2010,10(1):105-109. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2010/281925>
- XII. Bradshaw S, Habibollahi P, Soni J, Kolber M, Pillai AK. Popliteal artery entrapment syndrome.

Popliteal Artery Entrapment Syndrome. Case Report in an Elderly Patient

Cardiovasc Diagn Ther. 2021;11(5):1159-1167.
<https://doi.org/10.21037/cdt-20-186>

<https://doi.org/10.5758/vsi.230077>

- XIII. Al-Tayef TA, Rziki A, Rasras H, El Mahi O, Benzirar A. Popliteal artery entrapment syndrome: a case report with literature review. *Pan Afr Med J.* 2021;39:80.
<https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2021.39.80.27536>
- XIV. Stearns SA, Engmann TF, Francalancia S, Hegermiller K, Bixby S, Mandeville R, et al. Surgical management of popliteal artery entrapment syndrome. *J Orthop.* 2023;48:32-37.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jor.2023.11.023>
- XV. Kim HJ, Huh S, Kim HK. Popliteal Artery Entrapment Syndrome Presented with Popliteal Artery Pseudoaneurysm: A Case Report. *Vasc Specialist Int.* 2023;39:1.